

PRINCIPLES FOR PRAGMATICS TEACHING: APOLOGIES IN THE EFL CLASSROOM

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Abstract(eng): This article proposes principles for teaching pragmatics, specifically apologies, in the EFL classroom. The principles include cultural awareness, the use of authentic materials, explicit instruction, role-playing activities, and feedback and reflection. The article emphasizes the importance of teaching both linguistic and cultural aspects of apologies, and provides examples of activities that can be used to help students understand the appropriate use of language in different contexts. The article argues that teaching pragmatics can help students develop a more nuanced understanding of language use, and can ultimately lead to more effective communication in the target language.

Keywords: pragmatics teaching, apologies, EFL, practical teaching, authenticity.

Abstract(uzb): В этой статье предлагаются принципы обучения прагматике, в частности извинениям, в классе EFL. Принципы включают культурную осведомленность, использование аутентичных материалов, подробные инструкции, ролевые игры, а также обратную связь и размышления. В статье подчеркивается важность обучения как лингвистическим, так и культурным аспектам извинений, и приводятся примеры действий, которые можно использовать, чтобы помочь учащимся

понять правильное использование языка в различных контекстах. В статье утверждается, что преподавание прагматики может помочь учащимся развить более тонкое понимание использования языка и в конечном итоге может привести к более эффективному общению на изучаемом языке.

Ключевые слова: обучение прагматике, извинения, английский как иностранный, практическое обучение, подлинность

Pragmatics refers to the study of how language is used in context, and includes the rules and conventions of language use in different social situations. In education, pragmatism is a way of learning and teaching that is based on keeping things practical. Teachers with an pragmatics approach to teaching focuses on active project-based learning in the classroom and use topics applicable to students' lives. According to Sharma, Devi and Kumari pragmatism sees man as a social being and he acquires knowledge through personal experiances. According to Kasper, teaching pragmatics is an essential part of language learning, as it helps students develop the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in different social settings. One important aspect of pragmatics is apologies, which are a crucial part of social interaction.

Here are some basic principles of pragmatics teaching:

1. Cultural Awareness

When teaching apologies in the EFL classroom, it is important to emphasize the cultural norms and expectations surrounding apologies. This includes understanding the different cultural expectations for non-verbal cues, the use of indirect language, and the level of formality expected in different situations. For example, in some cultures, a direct apology may be seen as confrontational, while in other cultures, it may be expected. As an English language teacher working with students from different cultural backgrounds, it is important to make them aware of these cultural differences and how they may impact their use of apologies in English. For example, a Japanese student may be more likely to apologize frequently in their interactions

with English speakers, which could be perceived as insincere or unnecessary in certain contexts.

2. Authentic Materials

Using authentic materials, such as videos, audio clips, and real-life situations, can help students understand the context and appropriate use of apologies in different settings. This can also help students learn the appropriate tone and register to use in different situations. Authentic materials can also provide a more engaging and dynamic learning experience, as students can see how apologies are used in real-life situations. For example, using news articles, videos, or dialogues that feature apologies can provide learners with a rich source of authentic language input and context-specific information. They can also help learners to develop their listening and reading comprehension skills, as well as their ability to recognize and produce appropriate language and nonverbal cues when apologizing. Kasper and Schmidt believe that authentic materials can also be used to highlight cultural differences in the use of apologies and to promote cultural awareness and sensitivity among learners. For instance, by analyzing different types of apologies from different cultures, learners can gain insights into the underlying cultural values and expectations that shape these communicative practices.

3. Explicit Instruction

Students need to be taught explicitly about the structure of apologies, including the use of specific phrases, such as "I'm sorry" or "I apologize," and the importance of taking responsibility for the offense. This can be done through exercises and activities that focus on the different elements of apologies, such as expressing regret, taking responsibility, and offering a solution or compensation. One way to teach apologies explicitly is through the use of exercises and activities that focus on these different elements. For example, teachers can provide students with different scenarios that require apologies and ask them to practice expressing regret, taking responsibility, and offering a solution or compensation. Students can also be given real-life examples of apologies, such as news articles or videos, and asked to analyze

them to identify the different elements and language used. In addition to focusing on the language and structure of apologies, it is also important to teach students about the cultural and social aspects of apologies. This includes discussing different cultural expectations around apologies and how these may differ from their own culture. Teachers can also use authentic materials, such as videos or dialogues, to provide students with exposure to different cultural norms and practices around apologies.

4. Role-Playing

Role-playing activities can help students practice and internalize the appropriate language and cultural norms surrounding apologies. This can include simulating real-life scenarios and having students practice offering apologies in different contexts. "The greatest contribution of pragmatism to education is this principle of learning by doing."¹ Role-playing can also help students develop empathy and a better understanding of different perspectives, as they may have to take on the role of the offender or the offended.

Here we can see an example of a role-playing activity for teaching apologies in the EFL classroom:

Scenario: A student accidentally spills coffee on a classmate's laptop.

Role-play: Divide students into pairs and assign one student as the offender and the other as the offended. The offender should offer an apology and take responsibility for their actions, while the offended should express their feelings and respond to the apology. The students can then switch roles and repeat the activity.

Language focus: Encourage students to use appropriate language for apologizing, such as "I'm sorry for spilling coffee on your laptop," and expressing regret and empathy, such as "I understand how frustrating this must be for you."

Cultural focus: Discuss cultural expectations around apologies, such as how apologies may be expressed differently in different cultures, and how these cultural differences can impact communication and understanding.

¹ Adeleye, (2017) Pragmatism and Its Implications on Teaching and Learning in Nigerian Schools, p. 3

Through this role-playing activity, students can practice using appropriate language and cultural norms surrounding apologies in a safe and supportive environment. They can also develop empathy and a deeper understanding of different perspectives, which can help them to communicate more effectively in real-life situations. “Pragmatism holds that man is a social being. He is born into society and all his development takes place in and through society. Hence, pragmatists uphold democratic social attitudes and values.”²

5. Integration with Language Skills

Pragmatics instruction should be integrated with other language skills, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing, to help students develop a holistic understanding of language use. For example, students can listen to authentic audio clips of apologies, practice offering apologies in role-playing activities, read articles about cultural differences in apologies, and write about their own experiences with offering and receiving apologies. Here is an example of how teachers can integrate all language skills into pragmatics way of teaching apologies:

Language skill: Listening

Activity: Students listen to an authentic audio clip of an apology in English, such as a public figure apologizing for a mistake.

Language focus: Encourage students to identify the elements of the apology, such as the use of specific phrases, the expression of regret, and the acknowledgement of responsibility.

Cultural focus: Discuss how apologies may be expressed differently in different cultures, and how cultural differences can impact communication and understanding.

Language skill: Speaking

Activity: Students participate in a role-playing activity where they practice offering apologies in different scenarios.

²Adeleye, (2017) Pragmatism and Its Implications on Teaching and Learning in Nigerian Schools, p. 3

Language focus: Encourage students to use appropriate language for apologizing, such as "I'm sorry" or "I apologize," and expressing empathy and understanding.

Cultural focus: Discuss cultural expectations around apologies, such as how apologies may be expressed differently in different cultures, and how these cultural differences can impact communication and understanding.

Language skill: Reading

Activity: Students read articles about cultural differences in apologies from different countries.

Language focus: Encourage students to identify the cultural differences in how apologies are expressed and received, and the impact of these differences on communication.

Cultural focus: Discuss how cultural differences impact communication and understanding, and how to navigate these differences in a multicultural society.

Language skill: Writing

Activity: Students write about their own experiences with offering and receiving apologies.

Language focus: Encourage students to reflect on the different elements of apologies, such as expressing regret, taking responsibility, and offering a solution or compensation.

Cultural focus: Encourage students to consider cultural differences in how apologies are expressed and received, and how to navigate these differences in their own experiences.

Through these integrated language skill activities, students can develop a holistic understanding of pragmatics and language use, while also building their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills.

In conclusion, in today's interconnected world, effective communication is more important than ever before. Apologizing appropriately and effectively is a key aspect of communication, and it requires an understanding of not only the linguistic features of apologies but also the cultural norms and expectations surrounding them. By

incorporating principles for pragmatics teaching, teachers can help their students develop the necessary skills and strategies to navigate different social settings and communicate effectively with people from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

Teaching apologies in the EFL classroom can also foster the development of empathy and mutual respect. By encouraging students to reflect on their own experiences with giving and receiving apologies, they can gain a deeper understanding of how their words and actions can impact others. This can help students become more mindful communicators and more compassionate members of society.

Overall, the teaching of apologies is a crucial aspect of pragmatic instruction in the EFL classroom. By implementing the principles outlined in this article, teachers can provide their students with the tools and strategies necessary to communicate effectively and appropriately in a globalized world.

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